

Storage

Dry the seeds/grains thoroughly to a moisture content of <12% before storage. Store grains in clean sacks/bags free of weevils and placed in a dry, clean, well ventilated and rodent-proof store on raised benches/platforms.

Storage pest control

Stored pigeonpea grain is susceptible to attack by bruchids, *Callosobruchus* spp and these can cause up to 100% losses. Adult bruchids normally lay eggs on pods in the field and infestation continues during drying, in barnyards and under storage conditions. After hatching, the larvae burrow through the seed coats and develop within seeds and eat up the cotyledon, thereby causing extensive damage. Adult emerge from the seeds through characteristic holes made by the larvae.

Varieties

1. SEPI 1

Is medium duration (maturity about 150 days)
non determinate variety

2. SEPI 2

Is short duration (maturity about 120 days)
determinate variety.

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CLUSTER GRANARY SEED PROJECT NaSARRI

Pigeon Pea Production Guide

Funded by the:
European Union

Introduction

Pigeon pea is a shrub-like legume whose grain is rich in minerals, vitamins, fat and protein. It contains more minerals, 10 times more fat, 5 times more vitamin A, and 3 times more vitamin C than ordinary peas. It is also abundant in protein (up to 28%), making it an ideal supplement to traditional cereal-banana.

PRODUCTION PRACTICES

Seed bed preparation

The seedbed should be fine with proper drainage to ensure proper germination and timely prepared

Planting and spacing

This is done at the onset of rains as this will ensure good plant growth

use a row-row spacing of 75cm and plant-plant spacing of 25cm

seed rate of 18-20 kg/ha-1

Avoid late planting since this makes the crop vulnerable to pests and diseases. Early planted pigeon pea also takes full advantage of rains.

Sowing should be discouraged

Planting depth

5cm deep and covered firmly with soil to ensure a good contact between seed and soil particles and ultimately germination

Thinning

After 2-3 weeks from germination thinning to two plants per hill

Weed control

early weed control is recommended

three weedings 1)25-30 days, 2)50-60 days and 3)80-90 days.

Common diseases and management

- Fursarium wilt,
- cercospora leaf spot
- Powderly mildew

Cultural and chemical control

Field Pest management

- Pod borers (*Helicoverpa armigera* and *Maruca vitrata*),
- pod fly (*Melanagromyza obtusa*), pod suckers (*Clavigralla* spp),
- Aphids
- Blister beetle (*Mylabris pustule*).

These can be controlled by application of Cypermethrin 5 EC or a combination of Profenofos 40% +Cypermethrin 4% (100ml in 20L Knapsack sprayer) beginning at flower initiation/budding and subsequent sprays at 10-15 day intervals

HARVESTING, DRYING AND THRESHING

The crop can be harvested either by picking pods, cutting the pod-bearing branches, or by cutting the whole plant at ground level when about 75–80% pods are mature

Drying and threshing

The harvested materials should be left in the field for a few days to dry in the sun. Threshing can be done by heaping pods and beating them gently with sticks (care should be taken to avoid damaging the grains). Different varieties should be threshed on different days to avoid mixing up of varieties. After threshing, immature grains, chaff and other debris should be removed through winnowing.

Winnowing is done against the air drift so that the inert materials, such as chaff and broken seeds, are blown away by the wind and the grains are collected in a clean container/bag.

Hand Threshing

MANUAL

Manual Harvesting

MECHANICAL

Mechanical Harvesting

Pullman Thresher

Pullman Threshiner